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Analysis and Decision of Regional Economic Vitality and Its Influencing Factors

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ABSTRACT

It is important to understand the main factors that affect the economic vitality of a city, a province or even a country. These factors can guide the operation of policies and stimulate economic development. With the purpose of promoting Guangdong's economic development, the author explores and investigates the factors that affect Guangdong's economic vitality, in order to find the main factors that promote Guangdong's development. In this regard, the author will use factor analysis to extract the main components of the time data reflecting the economic development of Guangdong Province in the past 18 years, and then rename the obtained dimensionality reduction data. The data is ranked by the contribution rate, and the first factor that affects Guangdong's economic vitality is Guangdong's income and investment status, and the second factor is Guangdong's technological development status. The third factor is the labor force in Guangdong Province. Therefore, the author's suggestion for promoting Guangdong's economic development is to improve and regulate the labor market, increase technological innovation and attract investment.

INTRODUCTION

Regional economy is an important part of China's national economy, which is related to the overall situation of China's economic and social development. In the new period, the development of economic globalization and the sprint stage of the Double Hundred Plan have put forward higher requirements for China's regional economic development. Among them, General Secretary Xi Jinping explicitly stated in the report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China to "implement the strategy of coordinated regional development" and "establish a more effective new mechanism for coordinated regional development." Regional economic vitality and an army that enhances regional comprehensive competitiveness. Increasing economic vitality is the prerequisite for improving regional comprehensive competitiveness. Therefore, various regions have introduced many preferential policies to stimulate economic vitality, such as reducing the approval steps for investment promotion, providing financial support for start-ups, and lowering the entry threshold for attracting talents. However, the implementation of policies should be tailored to local conditions and can play a greater role in accordance with local development conditions. Based on this basis, relevant government departments need to seize the main factors, make decisions to maximize benefits, and effectively improve regional economic vitality. And our team will delve into this issue.

SYMBOL AND ASSUMPTIONS

Symbol Description

Symbol	Description
V_{ij}	Set of evaluation indicators for question one
S_{ij}	The object set of problem one research
F_k	Factor score for part one
μ_k	The contribution rate of each factor variance, that is, the weight

Fundamental Assumptions

- Since population migration is accompanied by the flow of talents, it is assumed that the net migration rate of talents is selected as the representative of the net migration rate of the population.
- Assume that corporate vitality is ultimately reflected in corporate profits.
- Assume that the selected economic transformation policy is independent, and the economic vitality it generates is not disturbed by other types of new economic policies.

AN EVALUATION MODEL OF THE FACTIONS AFFECTION THE ECONOMIC VITALITY OF GUANGDONG PROVINCE

Construction of Evaluation Index System

There are many evaluation methods for economic vitality, and the difference between these methods is mainly reflected in the establishment of an index evaluation system. Scholar Qiu Liyang et al. [1] used analytic hierarchy process and curve fitting to analyze the important factors affecting economic vitality and determine how to improve regional economic vitality. This method has a certain degree of subjectivity in weight construction, and the academic circles generally have a skeptical attitude towards this method. Scholar Zhou Yutong et al. [2] calculated and ranked the comprehensive scores of each city's economic vitality by establishing a weighted TOPSIS model. The entropy method was used to determine the weights of secondary indicators. This method also has a certain degree of subjectivity, but it is better than the first. This method is objective. The method used by the author is factor analysis. This method extracts the main factors that affect the city's economic vitality to the greatest extent, and achieves dimensionality reduction by extracting the same aspects of different factors. And the weight of each major factor is determined according to its contribution rate to economic vitality, which is more objective.

"Vitality" refers to the degree of support of a city, region or country for vital functions, ecological environment and economic society. Economic vitality, social vitality, environmental vitality, and cultural vitality together constitute the entire vitality system. [3] And regional economic vitality refers to the development capacity and potential of a regional economic development. If we want to comprehensively evaluate the factors that affect the economic vitality of Guangdong Province, we need to investigate from various aspects. In this paper, 12 indicators are constructed based on the 2000-2018 Statistical Yearbook of Guangdong Province (data for some missing years are obtained by fitting) and data from the National Bureau of Statistics to evaluate the influencing factors of Guangdong's economic vitality. The index system is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Evaluation index system of Guangdong's economic vitality

First-level indicators	Secondary indicators	Unit
Number of companies and benefits	Number of industrial enterprises above designated size	Each
	Total Profits of Industrial Enterprises Above Designated	100 Million Yuan

	Size	
Demographics	Natural population growth	%
	Net migration rate	%
Economic growth	GDP per capita	Yuan/person
	Local general public budget income per capita	Yuan/person
Education and technology level	Education expenditure as a percentage of fiscal expenditure	%
	Proportion of scientific research funds to fiscal expenditure	%
	Three patent applications	Each
	Three patent grants	Each
Resident income and employment status	Disposable income of capita	Yuan/person
	Unemployment rate	%

The indicators in the table are explained as follows:

(1) The number of enterprises and income reflects the micro-foundation of regional economic development. This indicator is divided into the number of industrial enterprises and the total profit of industrial enterprises above designated size. First, the number of industrial enterprises can explain the economic development of the region. Second, the total profit of industrial enterprises above designated size can reflect the economic value created by the industrial enterprises for the region.

(2) Demographic characteristics On the one hand, the natural growth rate of the population reflects the demand for labor in the region's economy. The sustained and healthy development of the economy can attract labor and cause population changes. Therefore, the trend of population change is also a reflection of regional economic vitality. [4] On the other hand, GDP per capita reflects the living standards of the people in the region, and the level of living reflects the level of economic development in the region.

(3) Economic growth means whether a city has the potential for economic growth and the potential for development. This level focuses on the future and explains the economic vitality of a city from a dynamic perspective. This is the primary factor in evaluating whether a city has economic vitality. [3] Therefore, it is mainly expressed in terms of per capita GDP and per capita fiscal revenue.

(4) The contribution of education and science and technology to regional economic vitality is necessary, and the level of education is the soul of regional economic vitality. It not only affects the quality of the labor force and the regional innovation ability, but also serves as the basis for the overall technological level of the region and affects the ability of technology to be transformed into productivity. The input of science and technology represents the region's innovation ability. Science and technology is the primary driving force for regional economic growth, and at the same time, it has great attraction for high-quality production factors outside the region. Therefore, we reflect this indicator from the local financial education and research expenditures, three patent applications, and three patent grants.

(5) Resident income and employment status can reflect people's living standards and regional labor force status. Resident income reflects the intensity of labor force in the region to a certain extent, and the sustained and stable growth of labor force is an important driving force for regional economic vitality. As the labor force continues to grow, the scale of production will gradually expand. Due to the existence of economies of scale, the region will achieve a higher rate of development, thereby forming a sustained economic growth. The unemployment rate reflects the degree of demand for labor in a region, and the scale and speed of economic development in the region.

Evaluation Methods of the Main Influencing Factors of Guangdong's Economic Vitality

This paper uses 2000-2018 Guangdong Statistical Yearbook and other time series data for factor analysis to extract the factors that affect the economic vitality of Guangdong Province.

(1) Establish the evaluation index, and set the research object set S_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 19$); the evaluation index set V_{ij} ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 12$).

(2) Perform a factor analysis on the time series data of S_{ij} , and extract the main component F_k of the factors that mainly affect Guangdong's economic vitality.

(3) Analyze and evaluate the obtained principal component and factor load matrix, and give an action plan to improve Guangdong's economic vitality. Combine the load matrix and the actual situation to analyze the changes in regional economic vitality from the perspective of population and corporate vitality trends influences. Before factor analysis is performed on the time series data of Guangdong Province from 2000 to 2018, the vector is normalized first, and the processing formula is

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_i^n y_{ij}^2}}$$

Factor Analysis and Results

Before performing the factor analysis, it is necessary to test the indicator system to check whether there is a significant correlation between the variables. If it does not exist, the factor analysis cannot be performed. This paper uses SPSS25 software to perform Cronbach's α value, KMO value and Bartlett sphericity test on time series data from 2000 to 2018. The test results are shown in Table 2

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett test

KMO and Bartlett test		
KMO Sampling Suitability	Quantities	.662
Bartlett sphericity test	Approximate chi-square	410.714
	Degrees of freedom	66
	Saliency	.000

Where α is equal to 0.830, the reliability of the sample data is credible. For structural validity, the KMO test value of each time series data is greater than 0.6, and the Bartlett spherical test value $P = 0.00$ is less than 0.05.

Common Factor Extraction for Each Time Series Data

The principal factor method was used to extract the common factors, and the time series data of Guangdong Province from 2000 to 2018 were calculated to obtain the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the correlation matrix. Here we extract common factors with eigenvalues greater than 1, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 :Total variance explanation

Ingredient	Initial eigenvalue			Extract load sum of squares			Sum of rotation load squares		
	Total	Variance percentage	Cumulative%	Total	Variance percentage	Cumulative%	Total	Variance percentage	Cumulative%
1	7.635	63.623	63.623	7.635	63.623	63.623	5.494	45.783	45.783
2	1.941	16.172	79.795	1.941	16.172	79.795	3.773	31.439	77.222
3	1.018	8.484	88.279	1.018	8.484	88.279	1.327	11.057	88.279
4	.603	5.023	93.302						
5	.421	3.509	96.811						

6	.215	1.793	98.603
7	.110	.917	99.521
8	.030	.253	99.773
9	.022	.181	99.954
10	.005	.040	99.994
11	.001	.004	99.998
12	.000	.002	100.000

There are three eigenvalues greater than 1, and the contribution rate of these three common factors is greater than 80%. At the same time, it can be seen from the gravel chart that the straight line connecting only three points is relatively steep, as shown in Figure 1 which also shows that the three common factors are selected, so the three common factors are highly representative.

Figure 1: Crushed stone

Time Series Data Factor Load Analysis

Due to the extraction of three common factors from the time series data of Guangdong Province from 2000 to 2018, the composition of the first common factor includes the number of industrial enterprises above designated size b_1 , the total profit of industrial enterprises above designated size b_2 , and the disposable income per capita b_3 , Unemployment rate b_4 , per capita GDP b_5 , the proportion of scientific research funds to fiscal expenditure b_6 , the education expenditure as a percentage of fiscal expenditure b_7 , and the per capita local general public budget revenue b_8 , so we named it Guangdong Provincial Income and Investment Status. The second common factor includes the number of patent grants b_9 , the natural population growth rate b_{10} , and the number of patent applications b_{11} , so we named it the state of technological development in Guangdong Province. The third common factor includes the population's net migration rate b_{12} , which we named the labor force situation in Guangdong Province. The details are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Rotated component matrix

	Symbolic representation	Ingredient		
		1	2	3
Number of Industrial Enterprises above Designated Size (%)	b_1	.879	.078	.272
Total profits of industrial enterprises above designated size (%)	b_2	.841	.434	-.239
Disposable income per capita (%)	b_3	.809	.507	-.214
Unemployment rate(%)	b_4	-.804	-.160	-.137
GDP per capita (%)	b_5	.794	.549	-.206
Proportion of scientific research funds to fiscal expenditure (%)	b_6	.781	.517	-.004
Education expenditure as a percentage of fiscal expenditure (%)	b_7	.778	-.046	-.148
Local general public budget income per capita (%)	b_8	.724	.597	-.269
Patent grants (%)	b_9	.149	.929	.222

Natural population growth rate (%)	b_{10}	.081	.916	.268
Patent applications (%)	b_{11}	.560	.788	-.110
Net migration rate (%)	b_{12}	-.044	.214	.928

Factor Comprehensive Score Calculation

Using regression analysis to calculate the final factor scoring coefficient matrix of Guangdong Province time series data from 2000 to 2018, we can get the scoring formula for the three common factors

$$F_1 = -0.164b_1 + 0.080b_2 + \dots - 0.152b_{12}$$

$$F_2 = -0.364b_1 - 0.028b_2 + \dots + 0.359b_{12}$$

$$F_3 = -0.100b_1 + 0.736b_2 + \dots + 0.71b_{12}$$

Then, the weighted summation of the variance contribution rate of the factors is used as the weight to obtain a comprehensive score of Guangdong's economic vitality from 2000 to 2018.

$$E_g(t) = \mu_k F_k, k = 1, 2, 3$$

The calculated comprehensive score of Guangdong's economic vitality is sorted by size as shown in Table 5.

Table5: Comprehensive score of Guangdong's economic vitality from 2000 to 2018

Year	Overall ratings	Year	Overall ratings
2002	-1.77	2013	0.11
2001	-1.67	2014	0.23
2012	-1.4	2017	0.67
2003	-1.24	2009	0.94
2015	-0.77	2010	0.94
2000	-0.6	2008	0.98
2004	-0.57	2006	1.3
2016	-0.45	2007	1.34
2005	0.11	2018	1.75
2011	0.11		

From the table, we can see that 2011, 2014, and 2015 (the data in 2012 actually reflects the situation in 2011, and so on). The overall score of Guangdong's economic vitality is relatively low. Analysis shows that Guangdong's net migration rate in the past three years has been relatively low. In particular, the net migration rate in 2011 was -1.7, which is already a negative value. This is because Guangdong was in the process of adjusting the industrial structure at that time, and it has not yet entered the right track. This has caused the overall profit of most companies to decline, the number of enterprises has also decreased significantly, the entire society has shown economic downturns, and the problem of difficult employment is frequent. Appeared, so a large number of laborers moved out in the early days. As a result, the industrial adjustment gradually entered the deep water area in the later stage. When labor and talents were needed to drive economic growth, it was found that the labor market was in short supply, which caused Guangdong's overall economic vitality to be low.

CONCLUSIONS: ACTION PLAN TO IMPROVE GUANGDONG'S ECONOMIC VITALITY

Through the above analysis, we can find that in order to effectively stimulate Guangdong's economic growth and improve Guangdong's economic vitality, it must be considered from the perspective of

population and enterprises. In terms of population, we all know that Guangdong Province, as a pioneer in reform and opening up, cannot develop without the vast number of inter-provincial migrant workers who moved to Guangdong for development, which means that most of Guangdong's labor force depends on migrant workers. As enterprises provide impetus for Guangdong's economic development, Guangdong Province should take the following measures:

(1) Improve the degree of marketization and improve the labor market for migrant workers

"Push-pull theory" is one of the important theories to study the floating population and immigration. Its basic view is that under the conditions of market economy and free movement of people, the factors that improve the living conditions of the floating population in the inflow region become the pulling force. The unfavorable socioeconomic conditions in the outflow areas become the thrust, and population migration is completed under the combined effect of these two forces. [5] This shows that the government should improve the living conditions of migrant workers and give them more care. At the same time, more relief labors for migrant workers' living difficulties were established. When the sluggish market economy caused a large number of migrant workers to lose their jobs, they were given some help. Only warm areas can retain labor. Of course, the most important task of the government is to increase market openness and regulate the rural labor market in order to attract rural mobile labor.

(2) Promote the integrated development of urban agglomerations

The negative net migration rate of Guangdong in 2011 mainly indicates that the urban agglomerations of Guangdong Province have a relatively small differentiation in the absorption of rural labor. Therefore, accelerating the integration of urban agglomerations can promote Guangdong's economic development. In the future development of Guangdong, we should always remember the division of labor and collaboration. Only in this way can we continuously generate new industrial chains in the region and extend the regional value chain, so as to enhance the overall economic competitiveness of the entire region, increase employment rates, and attract more The employment of immigrants promotes economic cycles and thus increases economic vitality.

(3) Increase the intensity of attracting investment and give certain high-tech enterprises settled certain benefits and preferential policies .

Enterprises are the driving force for the development of the regional economy. Only a sufficient number of enterprises can provide people with more jobs and drive the regional economy. And because Guangdong Province is currently suitable for the development of light industry and high-tech enterprises, the government should give policy support to the enterprises in which it resides, in order to improve Guangdong's economic vitality. Only by coordinating the resource allocation of the labor force and the enterprise in this way, can Guangdong's economic vitality be improved and can Guangdong's economic development be powered.

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